

Building a Sustainable System for Estonian Sign Language (EVK) Education in Estonia: EVKUR Recommendations 2025

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[[Estonian Sign Language Version](#)]

1. Introduction

Estonian Sign Language (EVK), as one of the legally recognised languages of Estonia, constitutes a central component of the country's linguistic ecology. Its development and institutionalisation are closely linked to questions of linguistic rights, educational equity, bilingual development, and accessible participation in social life. EVK education therefore represents not only a pedagogical issue, but also a matter of structured language planning and institutional design.

The EVKUR Recommendations 2025 build upon EVKUR Recommendations I (2024), which conceptualised the professionalisation of EVK education within a coherent national framework. They further draw on research conducted between 2024 and 2025, including the EVK Grammar Sketch and systematic literature review, sociolinguistic research on Deaf communities in Estonia, research on EVK teaching and assessment practices, and the development of language resources. Together, these outputs provide an empirical basis for coordinated action in corpus planning, acquisition planning, assessment planning, and digital resource development.

The present document seeks to move from descriptive analysis to structured implementation. It proposes a system-oriented approach to EVK education that integrates linguistic research, curriculum design, teacher preparation, assessment frameworks, and governance mechanisms into a coherent national strategy.

2. Strategic Orientation: EVK Education as Language Planning

The development of EVK education can be analytically understood through established dimensions of language planning.

Status planning concerns the positioning of EVK within national education and language policy frameworks, ensuring its institutional visibility and durability.

Corpus planning involves the systematic documentation and description of EVK through reference grammars, corpus-based inventories, and structured lexical resources.

Acquisition planning addresses curriculum design, differentiated learner pathways, teacher education, and lifelong learning structures.

Assessment planning focuses on transparent and standardised evaluation mechanisms aligned with the CEFR Companion Volume (CEFR-CV).

Digital resource planning encompasses the development of accessible, sustainable infrastructures that support teaching, learning, research, and certification.

The strategic objective is therefore to establish a coherent, inclusive, and competence-oriented EVK education system embedded within Estonia's broader language and education policies.

3. Governance and System Architecture

Effective language planning requires stable governance structures and clearly defined responsibilities. EVK education currently operates across multiple institutional levels, including schools, universities, professional associations, Deaf-led organisations, and government agencies. A coordinated steering structure would facilitate alignment across these actors, strengthen accountability, and ensure continuity beyond project cycles.

A phased implementation model is recommended. Pilot initiatives may serve as laboratories for curricular design, teacher qualification models, and assessment tools. Systematic evaluation should inform gradual scaling and institutionalisation. Transparent reporting and stakeholder consultation remain essential components of sustainable system development.

Such an approach contributes to building national capacity in EVK expertise, teacher preparation, corpus development, and digital infrastructure.

4. Core Areas of Development

4.1 Corpus and Pedagogical Infrastructure

A coherent EVK education system requires a shared linguistic foundation. At present, teaching practices rely on dispersed and locally developed materials, which may lead to variation and uneven quality. Corpus planning should therefore prioritise the development of a practical reference grammar, corpus-based lexical and structural inventories, and CEFR-aligned pedagogical guidance.

Structured teaching and learning materials derived from these resources would support consistency while allowing for regional and contextual adaptation. Regular revision cycles are essential to ensure responsiveness to new research findings and pedagogical experience.

4.2 Acquisition Pathways and Curriculum Design

EVK acquisition pathways are heterogeneous. They include Deaf children acquiring EVK as a first language, Deaf individuals encountering EVK later in life, hearing learners, and heritage signers. Acquisition planning must therefore be differentiated and modular.

CEFR-aligned curricula should articulate progression routes across educational stages and age groups. Early bimodal-bilingual pathways are particularly relevant for Deaf children and their families. Adult and heritage learners require structured access to systematic progression models that recognise diverse starting points and communicative needs.

4.3 Teacher Education and Professionalisation

Teacher preparation is a central mechanism of acquisition planning. A national EVK teacher competence framework would provide clarity regarding professional expectations and learning outcomes. A 30-ECTS micro-credential in EVK education and CEFR-aligned assessment could serve as an initial institutional pathway for qualification and upskilling.

In the medium term, the establishment of a BA programme in Estonian Sign Language Studies would contribute to sustainable workforce development. Such a programme would integrate

linguistic, pedagogical, and sociolinguistic components, strengthening long-term system capacity and professional stability.

4.4 Assessment and Certification

Assessment planning is necessary to ensure transparency, mobility, and comparability across educational contexts. A shared EVK assessment framework aligned with the CEFR-CV should include standardised rubrics, self-assessment tools, and video-based performance tasks that capture comprehension, production, interaction, and mediation.

A phased certification pathway beginning at A2 or B1 level may serve as an initial reference point, with gradual expansion across proficiency levels. This would strengthen both internal and external coherence within the EVK education system.

4.5 Sustainability and Policy Integration

Long-term viability depends on institutional anchoring and resource stability. EVK should be embedded explicitly within national language and education policy documents. Clear governance arrangements are required to define ownership, maintenance, and revision cycles for core resources.

A centralised digital EVK hub could integrate curricular materials, assessment tools, research outputs, and professional guidance. Such an infrastructure would support both pedagogical practice and language planning functions, while facilitating transparency and public accountability.

5. Anticipated Impact

The systematic integration of corpus, acquisition, assessment, and digital planning dimensions will strengthen the coherence of EVK education across educational levels and age groups. It will enhance professionalisation processes, stabilise teacher preparation pathways, and support evidence-based curriculum development.

By aligning national structures with international normative frameworks, including the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, and the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, Estonia reinforces its commitment to inclusive education and linguistic equity within a structured language planning paradigm.

6. Collaboration

The further development of EVK education requires sustained collaboration among Deaf-led organisations, professional associations, schools, universities, research institutions, and government partners. Continued research-based consultation and coordinated implementation are essential for maintaining coherence between empirical findings and institutional practice.